

Linear-Time Sequence Modeling with Selective State Space Mamba

Iheb Gafsi*
iheb.gafsi@insat.ucar.tn
INSAT

Discrete-Time Sequence:

In a discrete-time sequence modeling you typically have an input sequence $u_1 \dots u_L$ to predict the output sequence $y_1 \dots y_L$. To be able to do this you will need RNNs that are defined as:

$$x_k = \sigma(\bar{A}x_{k-1} + \bar{B}u_k)$$

$$y_k = \bar{C}x_k$$

where x_k is the hidden state vector and σ is an activation function.

Before the introduction of transformers this worked very well, as an example we can take ELMo.

Linear RNNs:

Linear RNNs are just a RNNs with a linear activation function so this means that: $x_k = \bar{A}x_{k-1} + \bar{B}u_k$ and $y_k = \bar{C}x_k$. By expanding this equation iteratively as follows:

$$x_k = \bar{A}x_{k-1} + \bar{B}u_k = \bar{A}^2x_{k-2} + \bar{A}\bar{B}u_{k-1} + \bar{B}u_k = \bar{A}^3x_{k-2} + \bar{A}^2\bar{B}u_{k-2} + \bar{A}\bar{B}u_{k-1} + \bar{B}u_k$$

$$x_k = \bar{A}^k x_1 + \bar{B} \sum_{n=1}^k \bar{A}^{k-n} u_n = \bar{B} \sum_{n=1}^k \bar{A}^{k-n} u_n$$

$$y_k = \bar{C}x_k = \sum_{n=1}^k \bar{C}\bar{B}\bar{A}^{k-n} u_n$$

So let the kernel sequence be:

$$\bar{K} = (\bar{C}\bar{B}, \bar{C}\bar{B}\bar{A}, \dots, \bar{C}\bar{B}\bar{A}^{L-1})$$

So specifically, we can apply this mathematically as applying a 1d convolution by the kernel and the input sequence, this can be used to optimize the training phase very quickly:

$$y = \bar{K} * u = \text{conv1d}(\bar{K}_L \dots \bar{K}_1, u_1 \dots u_L)$$

Practically, convolutions can be calculated more efficiently with the Fast Fourier Transform FFT since: $\mathcal{F}\{\bar{K} * u\} = \mathcal{F}\{\bar{K}\} \cdot \mathcal{F}\{u\}$ And then we would use the iFFT to get our result.

Using Linear RNNs is fast but it is not really that powerful because they are linear and their learning is really poor as they cannot shape with the real-world data.

Continuous-Time State Space Models SSMs:

An SSM is a continuous-time state space model looks very similar to RNNs but at a continuous time, defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}x'(t) &= \mathbf{A}x(t) + \mathbf{B}u(t) \\ y(t) &= \mathbf{C}x(t)\end{aligned}$$

This state space model is an LTI system (linear and time invariant). Usually, we never work with continuous signals (like sound), but always with discrete ones (because we sample them). Thus, we will discretize them to be able to work with them. Let's first talk about the Euler method for discretization As you know, the definition of a derivative is:

$$\frac{d}{dt}x(t) = \lim_{\Delta \rightarrow 0} \frac{x(t + \Delta) - x(t)}{\Delta}$$

Practically, we can't choose Δ to be equal to 0 however we can make it small enough to fit our solution, after that being done, we can say that:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{x(t + \Delta) - x(t)}{\Delta} &= \mathbf{A}x(t) + \mathbf{B}u(t) \\ x(t + \Delta) &= \Delta \mathbf{A}x(t) + x(t) + \Delta \mathbf{B}u(t) \\ x_{t+1} &= (\mathbf{I} + \Delta \mathbf{A})x_t + \Delta \mathbf{B}u_t = \bar{\mathbf{A}}x_t + \bar{\mathbf{B}}u_t\end{aligned}$$

Note that Δ is not a constant we choose but rather a learnable parameter during training.

However, in the paper instead of using the Euler method, they use the Zero-Order Hold (ZOH) rule to discretize the system which goes like follows. First, we define the discretization rule (φ_A, φ_B) so that $\bar{\mathbf{A}} = \varphi_A(\Delta, \mathbf{A}) = \exp(\Delta \mathbf{A})$ and $\bar{\mathbf{B}} = \varphi_B(\Delta, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) = (\Delta \mathbf{A})^{-1}(\exp(\Delta \mathbf{A}) - \mathbf{I}) \cdot \Delta \mathbf{B}$

Addressing Long-Range Dependencies:

Choosing the right A matrix to prevent the vanishing/exploding-gradient problem is crucial for our problem, and choosing a random value for A is what makes SSMs actually perform very poorly in practice. Intuitively for one reason which is that linear first-order ODEs solve to an exponential function $A \cdot A \cdot A \dots$ and thus may suffer from gradients scaling exponentially in the sequence length.

To address this problem, we will use the HiPPO to fill A. HiPPO theory isn't far from the intuition of Fourier transform but instead of approximating the function with weighted sines and cosines, we use the Legendre Polynomials. For which the formula is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}P_n(x) &= \frac{1}{2^n n!} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} (x^2 - 1)^n \\ &= \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k}^2 (x - 1)^{n-k} (x + 1)^k\end{aligned}$$

The next figure plots the first 5 Legendre Polynomials.

So as mentioned in the paper “HiPPO specifies a class of certain metrics $A \in R^{N \times N}$ that when incorporated into (1), allows the state $x(t)$ to memorize the history of the input $u(t)$. The most important matrix in this class is defined by equation (2), which we will call the HiPPO matrix. For example, the LSSL found that simply modifying an SSM from random A to equation (2) improved its performance on the sequential MNIST benchmark from 60% to 98%.”

$$A_{nk} = - \begin{cases} \sqrt{2n+1}\sqrt{2k+1} & \text{if } n > k \\ n+1 & \text{if } n = k \\ 0 & \text{if } n < k \end{cases}$$

Gu, A., Goel, K. and Ré, C., 2021. Efficiently modeling long sequences with structured state spaces. arXiv preprint arXiv:2111.00396

Selective SSM S6 Mamba:

The authors describe two tasks in which vanilla SSM or even the S4 (Structured State Space Model) does not perform well, and this dictates the motivation behind mamba. They are the Selective Copying and Induction Heads.

These tasks reveal the failure mode of the LTI models. From the recurrent view, their constant dynamics cannot let them select the correct information from their context, or affect the hidden state passed along the sequence an input-dependent way. From the convolutional view, it is known that global convolutions can solve the vanilla Copying task because of lack of content-awareness. More concretely, the spacing between inputs-to-outputs is varying and cannot be modeled by static convolution kernels.

Algorithm 1 SSM (S4)

Input: $x : (B, L, D)$
Output: $y : (B, L, D)$
1: $A : (D, N) \leftarrow \text{Parameter}$
▷ Represents structured $N \times N$ matrix
2: $B : (D, N) \leftarrow \text{Parameter}$
3: $C : (D, N) \leftarrow \text{Parameter}$
4: $\Delta : (D) \leftarrow \tau_\Delta(\text{Parameter})$
5: $\bar{A}, \bar{B} : (D, N) \leftarrow \text{discretize}(\Delta, A, B)$
6: $y \leftarrow \text{SSM}(\bar{A}, \bar{B}, C)(x)$
▷ Time-invariant: recurrence or convolution
7: **return** y

Algorithm 2 SSM + Selection (S6)

Input: $x : (B, L, D)$
Output: $y : (B, L, D)$
1: $A : (D, N) \leftarrow \text{Parameter}$
▷ Represents structured $N \times N$ matrix
2: $B : (B, L, N) \leftarrow s_B(x)$
3: $C : (B, L, N) \leftarrow s_C(x)$
4: $\Delta : (B, L, D) \leftarrow \tau_\Delta(\text{Parameter} + s_\Delta(x))$
5: $\bar{A}, \bar{B} : (B, L, D, N) \leftarrow \text{discretize}(\Delta, A, B)$
6: $y \leftarrow \text{SSM}(\bar{A}, \bar{B}, C)(x)$
▷ Time-varying: recurrence (*scan*) only
7: **return** y

$$s_B(x) = \text{Linear}_N(x), s_C(x) = \text{Linear}_N(x), s_\Delta(x) = \text{Broadcast}_D(\text{Linear}_1(x)), \tau_\Delta = \text{softplus}$$

Mamba model unfortunately cannot be trained with convolution because the model’s parameters differ for each input token. However, we still can use the scan operation when doing recurrence. And even enhance it with parallelization using the associativity property of our operations since $A * B * C = A * (B * C) = (A * B) * C$ so we can compile every pair in its own parallel thread, so by creating T threads, we reduce the time complexity from $O(N)$ to $O\left(\frac{N}{T}\right)$. This intuition was even developed to become “Selective Scan” with 2 more techniques: kernel fusion and recomputation.

Mamba Architecture:

Mamba model is built in such a way that it stacks multiple layers as shown below which is very similar to what Transformers look like. The architecture of Mamba is inspired by the Hungry Hungry Hippo (H3) architecture.

In a high level, this is what Mamba looks like:

Mamba Performance:

Model	Arch.	Layer	Acc.
S4	No gate	S4	18.3
-	No gate	S6	97.0
H3	H3	S4	57.0
Hyena	H3	Hyena	30.1
-	H3	S6	99.7
-	Mamba	S4	56.4
-	Mamba	Hyena	28.4
Mamba	Mamba	S6	99.8

Mamba has shown incredible results in selective copying, outperforming all of the models and showing that the Selective copying limit is no longer a problem to consider.

This table highlights the accuracy for combinations of architectures and inner sequence layers.

The Induction heads was a hard task for state space models to address especially for long sequences. As this graph shows, Mamba made it to the top.